

Assessment of machine learning techniques for analyzing land use changes and their erosive impacts in a dam basin

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807912>

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Abstract: The construction of dams, despite their social and economic benefits, also has drawbacks that become evident over time and are difficult to mitigate. One of these impacts is land use changes, which occur after the dam reservoirs are filled, leading to alterations in land use. These changes contribute to soil erosion, which not only results in the loss of valuable soil but also reduces the surface area and productivity of the land, leading to a decline in agricultural output. The aim of this research is to examine land use changes and soil erosion in the Gotvand Dam watershed in Khuzestan province. For the purpose of this study, a series of Landsat sensor images will be utilized. The research will employ a machine learning algorithm (ML) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classifying the images and analyzing land use changes. Additionally, the RUSLE model will be used to estimate erosion. By identifying and assessing land use changes and estimating erosion, valuable information can be obtained. This information can be useful for managers and officials in managing natural resources and promoting their sustainable development, which can be achieved through remote sensing technology and geographic information systems (GIS).

Keywords: *Dam, Land Use Changes, SVM, Erosion, RUSLE Model*

1. Introduction

One of the major challenges faced by humanity in the 21st century is the environmental crisis and the destruction of natural resources. The construction of large dams has significant environmental impacts, one of the most important being land-use changes. These changes are largely driven by rapid population growth and urbanization, which lead to alterations in land use, subsequently causing soil erosion. Dam construction has been a long-standing practice in various countries such as Japan, the United States, Spain, and China. In Iran, the construction of water transfer structures peaked between the years 1961 and 1991, with numerous instances of their adverse effects observed in different regions [1]. Studies conducted on areas where dams have been built consistently highlight common issues such as soil degradation and erosion, water pollution caused by sediment accumulation, the emergence of multiple diseases due to water contamination, and the destruction of habitats for plant and animal species. These impacts underline the undeniable effects of dam construction on the economic, health, and social aspects of communities [2]. To study land-use changes and their erosive effects, remote sensing data and geographic information systems (GIS) can be utilized. The application of such data and techniques plays a crucial role in preserving and managing natural resources effectively.

The rapid population growth in recent decades, and consequently the increasing demand for food and water, has driven humanity to bring more land under cultivation and use. Naturally, this land requires water, which is primarily made available by controlling river flows through the construction of dams [3]. For a dry country like Iran, dam construction is essential, allowing water to be stored to ensure a reliable source for meeting domestic, industrial, and agricultural needs, controlling floods, and generating hydroelectric power. Hence, dams are vital for the country's socio-economic development. While dams have contributed to significant benefits, their construction has also led to numerous negative environmental impacts [4]. In other words, although dams and water transfer structures have provided socio-economic advantages and numerous benefits, they have also caused damages that are difficult to reverse over time. One such impact is land use changes, as the establishment of a dam reservoir creates conditions

conducive to various land-use transformations [5]. One of the most significant environmental impacts of dam construction is land use changes [6]. Land use changes may be one of the greatest challenges facing humanity, driven by exploitation and greed for more resources. In recent years, extensive research has been conducted on the impact of land use and land management on surface runoff, soil erosion, and sediment yield, with many studies identifying land use as the most critical factor influencing soil erosion [7]. In other words, soil erosion in a region is influenced by various factors, including climate conditions, topography, soil type, and land use, with land use being the most significant among these factors [8]. Today, soil erosion caused by land use changes has become the most critical issue in land degradation worldwide, with its consequences including landform alteration and disruption of ecosystem functions [9]. Parvar et al. [10] conducted a study to monitor the changes caused by the construction of the Shirin Darreh Dam on the land cover and land use in the downstream watershed. The results demonstrated the efficiency and effectiveness of remote sensing methods in detecting and monitoring changes in land cover and land use. Similarly, Feyzizadeh [11] modeled land-use changes and their impacts on the erosion system in the Alavian Dam basin. The findings of this research indicated that satellite imagery possesses a high capability for evaluating land-use change trends and can serve as a basis for assessing environmental changes, making it applicable in various studies. The use of remote sensing data and geographic information systems (GIS) can provide valuable insights into land use changes and their optimal management [12]. Moreover, understanding the trend of land use changes can help take steps toward preventing soil erosion and guiding ecosystems toward balance and sustainability [13]. Remote sensing technology holds a special position in natural resource studies. Multi-temporal comparisons, up-to-date information, digital processing, data diversity, and rapid data transmission have made remote sensing the most important technology for change detection [11]. The purpose of this research is to analyze land use changes and erosion using a series of Landsat satellite sensor images. To conduct this research, machine learning algorithms, specifically the Support Vector Machine (SVM), and the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model will be utilized.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The area examined in this study is the Gotvand Dam watershed. Gotvand Dam is one of the largest dams in Iran and the second largest water reservoir in the country (after Karkheh Dam), and it holds the largest water reservoir on the Karun River [14]. The geographical location of Gotvand Dam is at 48°56'10" E longitude and 32°16'8" N latitude, situated 380 kilometers from the mouth of the Karun River and 10 kilometers northeast of the city of Gotvand in Khuzestan Province. The construction of diversion tunnels for the Gotvand Dam project began in May 1997, and the main construction work on the dam commenced in 2001 [15].

Figure 1. Study area

2.2. Data

In this study, the data utilized includes a time series of Landsat images, the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the study area from the ASTER satellite, and climatic information from CHIRPS satellite data (Table 1).

Additionally, Google Earth Engine was used for data processing and analysis, and ArcMap software was employed for output generation and creating the final map.

Table 1. Data

Data	Date	Reference
Landsat7	2003	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
Landsat8	2013	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
Landsat8	2023	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
CHIRPS	2003	ftp://ftp.chg.ucsb.edu
CHIRPS	2013	ftp://ftp.chg.ucsb.edu
CHIRPS	2023	ftp://ftp.chg.ucsb.edu
ASTER	-	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/

2.3. Research Methodology

The research process in this study is based on various operational phases, which can generally be divided into four stages as follows:

- 1) Pre-processing operations, including radiometric and atmospheric corrections of the Landsat images.
- 2) Implementation of classification algorithms on the images to generate the desired maps.
- 3) Validation operations to determine the accuracy and precision of the results.
- 4) Estimation of soil erosion using the RUSLE model.

Each of these methods and operational phases is explained in detail in the following sections.

2.3.1. Satellite Image Preprocessing

After acquiring data from the sensor, the process of analyzing the data is conducted to extract information from these datasets for various applications. The analysis process includes several preprocessing steps that ultimately lead to the extraction of useful information. In the preprocessing stage, errors in the raw data, such as radiometric, atmospheric, geometric, and other types of errors, are corrected [16].

2.3.2. Land Use Classification

Classification is one of the main objectives of satellite image processing, with the final result usually being thematic maps in which each pixel is assigned to a specific class of objects (such as land cover or land use) [17]. In this research, to analyze land use changes in the Gotvand Dam watershed, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm has been employed. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a classification method based on a supervised hyperplane separator. Simply put, SVM is a separator or boundary that best distinguishes the data. One of the advantages of the SVM method is its ability to handle high-dimensional data efficiently, and by selecting an appropriate kernel, it can achieve optimal performance [18]. The SVM classification algorithm is a supervised algorithm for analyzing satellite image data, which, in addition to its high accuracy, also has a relatively fast execution speed, making it popular among researchers in recent years. This algorithm is essentially a binary classifier that separates two classes using a linear boundary and is part of the generalized linear classifiers.

2.3.3. Validation (Accuracy Assessment)

Accuracy assessment or validation is a key component of any study utilizing geospatial data and satellite imagery. This assessment is crucial for several reasons, such as understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the analysis, correcting errors, enabling quantitative and qualitative comparisons of analytical methods, and ensuring the usability of the information derived from data analysis in decision-making processes [19]. No classification can be deemed reliable unless its accuracy has been evaluated. This evaluation is done through pixel sampling as spectral or informational class patterns, allowing simultaneous assessment of spectral class reflectance and their separability [20]. Therefore, to ensure the accuracy of the classification, an accuracy assessment is conducted. Classification accuracy refers to the level of confidence obtained from the ratio of evaluated pixels in the classification to a set of ground truth data collected by the interpreter [17].

In the present study, since the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm is employed, it is necessary to perform an accuracy assessment to determine the algorithm's precision and reliability. For this purpose, an error matrix was used, and various parameters such as overall accuracy, kappa coefficient, user accuracy, and producer accuracy were extracted.

2.3.4. Soil Erosion Assessment

In this research, the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model was used to estimate the average annual soil erosion. The RUSLE model is widely applied globally to predict long-term rill and interrill erosion at scales ranging from farms to watersheds under various management practices [21]. The Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) is an empirical model extensively used to study the factors affecting water erosion and to estimate soil loss due to surface and rill erosion from agricultural lands. The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) is a developed version of USLE, used for predicting the annual soil erosion from a given surface [22]. Soil erosion based on the RUSLE model is calculated using the following equation (1):

$$A = R * K * LS * C * P \quad (1)$$

Where:

A is the amount of soil eroded due to sheet and rill erosion, expressed in mass per unit area over time.

R is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor.

K is the soil erodibility factor, indicating the inherent sensitivity of the soil to erosion.

L is the slope length factor.

S is the slope steepness factor.

C is the cover-management factor.

P is the support practice factor.

In this relationship, A is measured in tons per hectare per year, R in megajoules per millimeter per hectare per hour per year, K in tons per hour per megajoule per millimeter, and P, C, S, and L are dimensionless [23].

In this study, the Google Earth Engine platform was utilized to operationalize the RUSLE model and estimate soil erosion in the Ghotound Dam basin. Each of the RUSLE model parameters was estimated within this platform using coding. Finally, by integrating and combining all parameters, the soil erosion layer for the study area was produced.

3. Results

3.1. Results of Land Use Classification

In this study, Landsat ETM+ and OLI time series images were used to assess land use changes in the Getvand Dam basin. These images are accessible from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) database. Due to their suitable spatial and spectral resolution, the long history of the time series, and their availability for free, these images are considered the most appropriate tools for examining land use changes. Three images from the years 2003, 2013, and 2023 were used in this research.

3.1.1. Results of Land Use Classification for the Year 2003

According to Figure 2-3 and Table 2, the area of land use in the Getvand Dam basin in 2003 is as follows:

Water Use, 7.01 hectares, accounting for 1.16% of the total area. Barren Land, 469.39 hectares, representing 77.93% of the total area. Agricultural Land, 123.77 hectares, comprising 20.55% of the total area. Residential Areas, 2.13 hectares, which constitutes 0.35% of the total area. These results illustrate the distribution of various land uses within the basin and provide a baseline for analyzing changes in land use over subsequent years.

Table 2. Land Use Area of the Gandoman Dam Basin in 2003

Land Use Type	Area (Hectares)	Percentage
Water	7.01	1.16%
Barren Land	469.39	77.93%
Agricultural Land	123.77	20.55%
Residential Areas	2.13	0.35%

Figure 2. Land use area chart for 2003 based on: a) hectares, b) percentage

Figure 3. Land use map of the Gotvand Dam basin in 2003

3.1.2. Results of Land Use Classification for the Year 2013

The results of the land use classification for 2013 indicate that (according to Figure 4-5 and Table 3):

Water Use, 11.66 hectares, accounting for 1.94% of the total area. Barren Land, 430.94 hectares, representing 71.55% of the total area. Agricultural Land, 154.87 hectares, comprising 25.71% of the total area.

Residential Areas, 4.84 hectares, which constitutes 0.80% of the total area.

These results reflect the distribution of different land uses within the basin for 2013 and facilitate comparisons with previous and future years.

Table 3. Land Use Area of the Gattund Dam Basin in 2013

Land Use	Area (Hectares)	Percentage
Water	11.66	1.94%
Barren Land	430.94	71.55%
Agricultural Land	154.87	25.71%
Residential Areas	4.84	0.80%

Figure 4. Land use area chart for 2013 based on: a) hectares, b) percentage

Figure 5. Land use map of the Gotvand Dam basin in 2013

3.1.3. Results of Land Use Classification for the Year 2023

Figure 6-7 and Table 4 indicate that the land use area within the Ghandab Dam basin in 2023 is as follows:

Water Use, 15.26 hectares, accounting for 2.53% of the total area. Barren Land, 378.65 hectares, representing 62.87% of the total area. Agricultural Land, 202.36 hectares, comprising 33.60% of the total area. Residential Areas, 6.03 hectares, which constitutes 1% of the total area.

These results demonstrate the distribution of different land uses within the basin for 2023 and enable comparisons with earlier years.

Table 4. Land Use Area of the Gattund Dam Basin in 2023

Land Use	Area (Hectares)	Percentage (%)
Water	15.26	2.53%
Barren Land	378.65	62.87%
Agricultural Land	202.36	33.60%
Residential Areas	6.03	1.00%

Figure 6. Land use area chart for 2023 based on: a) hectares, b) percentage

Figure 7. Land use map of the Gotvand Dam basin in 2023

3.4. Results of Land Use Classification Accuracy Assessment

To evaluate the accuracy of the classification results, an error matrix was employed. For this purpose, training samples were applied to the image, and then the overall accuracy, user accuracy, producer accuracy, and Kappa statistic were used to validate the results. High values close to 100% for overall accuracy and a Kappa value of

1 indicate high credibility of the results. Based on the obtained results (Table 5-7), the overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient for land use classification in 2003 were 95.22% and 0.93, respectively. For land use in 2013, the overall accuracy was 90.0%, and the Kappa coefficient was 0.86. Additionally, the accuracy assessment results for land use classification in 2023 indicated an overall accuracy of 95.06% and a Kappa coefficient of 0.93.

Table 5. Accuracy Assessment of Land Use Classification for 2003 (%)

Land Use	Producer's Accuracy (%)	User's Accuracy (%)
Barren Land	100	86.36
Agricultural Land	80	100
Residential Areas	70	100
Water	100	100
Overall Accuracy	95.22	

Table 6. Accuracy Assessment of Land Use Classification for 2013 (%)

Land Use	Producer's Accuracy (%)	User's Accuracy (%)
Barren Land	100	76.92
Agricultural Land	80	94.12
Residential Areas	70	100
Water	100	100
Overall Accuracy	90.00	

Table 7. Accuracy Assessment of Land Use Classification for 2023 (%)

Land Use	Producer's Accuracy (%)	User's Accuracy (%)
Barren Land	100	87.50
Agricultural Land	100	95.24
Residential Areas	80	100
Water	100	100
Overall Accuracy	95.06	

3.2. Results of Soil Erosion Estimation

The average annual soil erosion is calculated as the product of the erosion factors: Rainfall erosivity (R), Soil erodibility (K), Vegetation cover management (C), Topography (LS), and Conservation practices (P), using Equation (1) in the Google Earth Engine environment. The annual soil erosion values are estimated in tons per hectare per year for the three time periods: 2003, 2013, and 2023. According to Figure (8-10), the annual soil erosion values in the study area in 2003 ranged between 0 and 536 tons per hectare per year. In 2013, as shown in Figure (4-8), the soil erosion amount was 0 to 662 tons per hectare per year, and for 2023, based on Figure (4-9), the erosion value was 0 to 778 tons per hectare per year. This indicates that, following the construction of the Gotvand Dam, soil erosion in the study area has increased from 2003 to 2023.

Figure 8. Soil erosion map of the Gotvand Dam basin in: a) 2003, b)2013, c)2023

3.3. Assessment of the Effects of Land Use Changes on Soil Erosion

To evaluate the effects of land use on soil erosion, it is essential to integrate the erosion model layers and land use data using the "Zonal Statistics as Table" extension in ArcMap. The results of this integration calculate the soil loss for each land use type present in the Gotvand Dam basin for the years 2003, 2013, and 2023. The results in Table 8 indicate that in 2003, water land use had the highest average erosion at 26.29 tons per hectare per year, while agricultural land use had the lowest average erosion at 0.81 tons per hectare per year. According to Table 9, in 2013, water and agricultural land use again had the highest and lowest average erosion, respectively, with values of 57.55 and 0.86 tons per hectare per year. Additionally, Table 10 shows that in 2023, the highest average erosion was associated with water land use, with an erosion rate of 59.77 tons per hectare per year, while residential areas had the lowest erosion rate at 0.77 tons per hectare per year.

Overall, the results of assessing the effects of land use changes on soil erosion indicate that over the 20-year period, the average erosion for barren land has decreased, while the average erosion for agricultural land has increased. This can be attributed to the conversion of barren land into agricultural land. Furthermore, during this 20-year period, water land use has experienced the highest average soil erosion.

Table 8. Average Soil Erosion for Land Use in (2003, 2013, 2023)

	Land Use	Area (Hectares)	Percentage	Average Erosion Rate (Tons per Hectare per Year)
2003	Water	7.01	1.16%	26.29
	Barren Land	469.39	77.93%	3.31
	Agricultural Land	123.77	20.55%	0.81
	Residential Areas	2.13	0.35%	1.80
2013	Water	11.66	1.94%	57.55
	Barren Land	430.94	71.55%	2.98
	Agricultural Land	154.87	25.71%	0.86
	Residential Areas	4.84	0.80%	6.06
2023	Water	15.26	2.53%	59.77
	Barren Land	378.65	62.87%	2.37
	Agricultural Land	202.36	33.60%	0.92
	Residential Areas	6.03	1.00%	0.77

4. Discussion

The construction of dams, while offering significant economic benefits, also presents various environmental drawbacks, with one of the most critical being changes in land use. These changes become evident over a long-term period following the initiation of reservoir filling and dam development, subsequently leading to soil erosion. In other words, land use changes are among the most influential factors affecting soil erosion, significantly impacting its extent. This study aims to investigate the impact of land use changes on soil erosion in the Gotvand Dam basin. To achieve this, land use maps were generated using time series images from Landsat ETM+ and OLI, employing the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm. The classification was conducted into four land use classes: barren land, water, residential areas, and agricultural land for the period from 2003 to 2013. Additionally, to assess the risk of soil erosion in the land use units of the Gotvand Dam basin, the RUSLE model was implemented within a Geographic Information System (GIS) framework, utilizing remote sensing technology. Each of the factor's C, LS, K, R, and P was calculated and integrated in the Google Earth Engine environment to estimate soil erosion and obtain the spatial distribution of erosion across different sections of the Gotvand Dam basin. The findings of this research revealed that the most significant changes pertained to barren land and agricultural land. Specifically, the area of agricultural land increased from 31.1 hectares in 2013 to 47.49 hectares in 2023, while barren land area decreased by 38.45 hectares in 2013 and 52.29 hectares in 2023. The estimated soil erosion using the RUSLE model for the years 2003, 2013, and 2023 was 0.536, 0.662, and 0.778 tons per hectare per year, respectively, indicating an increasing trend in erosion within the study area. Moreover, the assessment of land use change effects on erosion showed a decrease in average soil erosion for barren land from 2003 to 2023, while there was an increase in average erosion for agricultural land, likely due to the conversion of barren land to agricultural use. Additionally, water use showed the highest average erosion during this period. The results of this study are significant for understanding the dynamics of land use changes and their impact on soil erosion in the Gotvand Dam basin. The observed increase in agricultural land and the associated rise in soil erosion emphasize the need for implementing sustainable land management practices. The conversion of barren land into agricultural fields, while beneficial for local economic development, has inadvertently increased soil erosion rates, as agricultural activities often disturb the natural soil structure and expose it to erosion. The findings also highlight the role of water bodies in exacerbating erosion, which could be linked to changes in water flow patterns and sediment transport caused by the presence of the dam. The increase in erosion in areas adjacent to water bodies warrants further investigation into the hydrological impacts of dam construction on surrounding landscapes. However, this study provides new insights into the specific impact of land use changes in the Gotvand Dam basin, utilizing high-resolution satellite imagery and advanced machine learning techniques to produce more accurate land use maps and erosion estimates. Future research could focus on exploring the effectiveness of specific erosion control techniques in the Gotvand Dam basin. Given the increasing trends in erosion, further studies should examine the potential of using vegetative cover, terracing, and other soil conservation methods to mitigate the adverse effects of land use changes. Additionally, investigating the impact of climate change on erosion patterns in the basin could provide valuable insights, as changing rainfall patterns and temperature fluctuations may exacerbate soil erosion risks. Moreover, the integration of machine learning techniques, such as deep learning algorithms for better classification accuracy and predictive modeling of erosion, could be explored to enhance the precision of future land use and erosion assessments. Overall, the results of this study can be valuable for organizations and authorities involved in environmental and soil management. By identifying erosion-prone areas, appropriate measures can be implemented to mitigate soil erosion effectively. The findings underscore the importance of monitoring land use changes in dam basins and their direct correlation with soil erosion, which can significantly impact both environmental sustainability and land productivity.

5. Conclusion

In recent decades, the utilization of modern remote sensing techniques and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has become a valuable tool for users in the field of natural resource studies and environmental management. The application of these techniques has facilitated the processes of management and planning, helping to control or mitigate risks associated with various environmental hazards.

The results of this study indicated that the use of Landsat time series images, due to their suitable spatial and spectral resolution, long historical availability, and cost-free access, represents the most appropriate tool for analyzing land use changes. In this research, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm was employed to investigate land use changes, and the RUSLE model was used to estimate erosion in the Ghotound Dam basin, yielding favorable results. Therefore, the findings of this research can be valuable for managers and relevant authorities, enabling them to identify and analyze land use changes and recognize areas prone to erosion. This can lead to appropriate management actions and strategies for soil conservation and erosion prevention. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended to employ additional methods and algorithms for a more precise examination of the impact of land use changes on erosion. Furthermore, other models and methods could be utilized to estimate erosion in the Ghotound Dam basin, allowing for a comparison of results to enhance the overall understanding and outcomes.

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